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**PREVALENCE OF URINARY
INCONTINENCE AMONG PATIENTS
PRESENTING IN THE UROLOGY
OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

Urinary incontinence (UI), often known as involuntary urination, is any uncontrolled flow of urine. It is a frequent and distressing problem, which may have a substantial influence on quality of life. The goal of this study was to assess the prevalence of urine incontinence among the patients coming in urology outside department. This cross-sectional study was carried out on patients who presented to the urology outdoor department of various hospitals. On a predefined proforma, the name, age, gender, and symptoms of presentation, as well as the duration of symptoms, were recorded. A total of 135 patients presenting in urology outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 83 (61%) males and 52 (39%) females. The mean age of the patients was 35.42±4.02 years. Out of 83 males, 21 males were having urinary incontinence and out of 52 females, 16 were having urinary incontinence.

Keyword: Urinary Incontinence

INTRODUCTION:

Urinary incontinence (UI), often known as involuntary urination, is any uncontrolled flow of urine. It is a frequent and distressing problem, which may have a substantial influence on quality of life. It has been noted as a major concern in geriatric health care. The term enuresis is often used to refer to urine incontinence especially in children, such as nocturnal enuresis (bed wetting) (bed wetting).

Pelvic surgery, pregnancy, delivery, and menopause are substantial risk factors. Urinary incontinence is typically a result of an underlying medical issue but is under-reported to medical practitioners. There are four main types of incontinence i.e., urge incontinence due to an overactive bladder, stress incontinence due "a poorly functioning urethral sphincter muscle (intrinsic sphincter deficiency) or to hypermobility of the bladder neck or urethra", overflow incontinence due to either poor bladder contraction or blockage of the urethra and mixed incontinence involve features of different other types

Treatments include pelvic floor muscle training, bladder training, surgery, and electrical stimulation. Behavioral treatment often performs better than medicine for stress and urge incontinence. The benefit of drugs is limited, and long-term safety is questionable. Urinary incontinence is more common in elderly women (1-3). The goal of this study was to assess the prevalence of urine incontinence among the patients coming in urology outside department.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was carried out on patients who presented to the urology outdoor department of various hospitals. On a predefined proforma, the name, age, gender, and symptoms of presentation, as well as the duration of symptoms, were recorded. SPSS Ver. 23.0 was used to enter and analyse all of the data. The quantitative variables were presented in the form of a mean

and a standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented in the form of frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 135 patients presenting in urology outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 83 (61%) males and 52 (39%) females. The mean age of the patients was 35.42 ± 4.02 years. The main symptom of presentation was uncontrolled flow of urine. The minimum duration of symptoms was nine months, and the maximum duration was five years. Out of 83 males, 21 males were having urinary incontinence and out of 52 females, 16 were having urinary incontinence.

DISCUSSION:

Continence and micturition require a delicate balance of urethral closure and detrusor muscle activity (the muscle of the bladder). During urination, the bladder wall's detrusor muscles contract, forcing urine out of the bladder and into the urethra. Simultaneously, the urethral sphincter muscles relax, allowing urine to exit the body. The urethral sphincter is a muscular ring that closes the urinary bladder outlet, preventing urine from passing outside the body. Normally, urethral pressure exceeds bladder pressure, causing urine to remain in the bladder and maintaining continence. The urethra is held in place by the pelvic floor muscles and tissue, allowing it to close tightly. Any disruption in the balance between the detrusor muscle, urethral sphincter, supportive tissue, and nerves can result in incontinence.

For example, stress urinary incontinence is usually caused by an ineffective urethral sphincter closure. Damage to the sphincter, the muscles that support it, or the nerves that supply it can all cause this. In men, the damage is typically caused by prostate surgery or radiation, whereas in women, it is typically caused by childbirth and pregnancy. The pressure inside the abdomen (from coughing and sneezing) is normally transmitted equally to

both the urethra and the bladder, leaving the pressure difference unchanged and resulting in continence. When the sphincter is ineffective, the increased pressure pushes the urine against it, resulting in incontinence.

Urge incontinence is another example. This incontinence is caused by sudden forceful contractions of the detrusor muscle (bladder muscle), which results in an intense feeling of urination and incontinence if the person does not use the restroom on time. The condition is known as overactive bladder syndrome, and it is caused by detrusor muscle dysfunction (4-5).

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